

RAISING THE LEGAL AWARENESS AND LEGAL CULTURE OF CITIZENS IN SOCIETY

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Abstract. *Raising the legal awareness and legal culture of citizens in society and their constitutional rights and duties, the essence of moral norms, political and legal devoted to the development of legal consciousness and culture, spiritual and enlightenment activities, religious and national values in youth, customs and traditions, involvement in events in our society, require the upbringing of young people in the spirit of patriotism, by the principles of patriotism and the rule of law, democratic state and free civil society, are the highest value facing our nation.*

Keywords: *society, citizen, legal, consciousness, culture, constitution, law, duty, morality, political, spiritual, enlightenment, youth, national, value, democratic, state.*

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ПРАВОСОЗНАНИЯ И ПРАВОВОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ ГРАЖДАН В ОБЩЕСТВЕ

Аннотация. *Повышение правосознания и правовой культуры граждан в обществе и их конституционных прав и обязанностей, сущность нравственных норм, политико-правовая направленность на развитие правосознания и культуры, духовно-просветительская деятельность, религиозные и национальные ценности у молодежи, обычаи и традиции, сопричастность к событиям в нашем обществе, требуют воспитания молодежи в духе патриотизма, на принципах патриотизма и правового государства, демократического государства и свободного гражданского общества, является высшей ценностью, стоящей перед нашим народом.*

Ключевые слова: *общество, гражданин, правовое, сознание, культура, конституция, право, долг, нравственность, политическое, духовное, просвещение, молодежь, национальное, ценностное, демократическое, государственное.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most pressing issues today is that the education of young people in our country has risen to the level of state policy. One of our main tasks is to protect the youth of our future from various alien ideas and aggression. Indeed, as noted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, “The upbringing of the younger generation has always been important and relevant. But in the 21st century we live in, this issue is becoming a matter of life and death” [2, pp. 504-505].

The development of modern civic literacy is related to the development of students' knowledge in legal, spiritual, educational, legal, and cultural terms. Pedagogical higher education institutions play an important role in the development of civic literacy of future teachers, cultivating in them high moral qualities, ideological maturity, citizenship, and patriotism. Therefore, pedagogy is one of the main tasks of higher education institutions, which reflects the development of civic literacy in students as a legal culture, legal consciousness, and its important factor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main legal basis for the development of science and its state support in our country is clearly defined by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Article 42 of Chapter IX, entitled "Economic and Social Rights" of the Constitution, guarantees the freedom of scientific and technical creativity, and the right to enjoy cultural achievements. The state shall take care of the cultural, scientific, and technical development of society." [1]

Article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy", adopted on September 14, 2016, defines the following as the main directions of state youth policy:

- ensuring the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of young people;
- protecting the lives and health of young people;
- to promote the spiritual, intellectual, physical, and moral development of young people;
- ensuring open and quality education for young people;
- creation of conditions for youth employment and employment;
- to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism, civic duty, tolerance, respect for the law, national and universal values, to have strong beliefs and views on life, able to resist harmful influences and currents;
- to protect young people from acts that violate moral principles, from ideas of terrorism and religious extremism, separatism, fundamentalism, violence, and cruelty;
- raising the level of legal awareness and legal culture of young people;
- support and encouragement of gifted and talented youth;
- creating conditions for the development of youth entrepreneurship;
- formation of aspirations of young people to a healthy lifestyle, as well as the creation of conditions for the meaningful organization of youth leisure and the mass development of youth sports;
- implementation of a comprehensive system of measures for the spiritual and material support of young families, the creation of decent housing and social conditions for them;
- development of cooperation with international organizations working in the field of realization of the rights and freedoms of youth [3].

These priorities show the need to prepare future young teachers for the spiritual and moral education of students by increasing their legal literacy, not only through the formation of competencies in science but also through ideological and legal, and moral competence.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 9, 2019 No PF-5618 "On radical improvement of the system of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society" identifies the following as the main tasks of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society:

- formation of a system of consistent communication of the content and essence of the ongoing socio-economic reforms, adopted legislation and state programs in the country, "Decision of the spirit of respect for the law in society - the key to building a democratic state governed by the rule of law!" strengthening the idea of life;
- in raising legal awareness and legal culture in society, first of all, pay special attention to the systematic and integrated implementation of education, deepening the legal consciousness and legal culture in all segments of the population, starting from preschool education, maintaining a balance between personal and public interests. advocacy tasks are assigned [4].

RESULTS

Raising the legal consciousness and legal culture of citizens in society and their constitutional rights and duties, the essence of moral norms, political and legal, spiritual and educational activities dedicated to the development of legal consciousness and culture, religious and national values, customs, and traditions in youth, Involvement in the events taking place in our society requires education by the principles of patriotism and the rule of law, democratic state and free civil society because educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is the highest value facing our nation.

At the solemn event dedicated to the 27th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev "The Constitution and the rule of law are the most important criteria of a democratic state and civil society", "No matter how perfect the laws we create, no matter what reforms we make, if the legal knowledge of our citizens, if the consciousness and culture are not sufficient, it will be difficult to achieve the expected results. Centuries ago, jurists wrote that "understanding the law develops a sense of responsibility", his wise words will never lose their relevance. In other words, respect for the Constitution and laws, legal consciousness, and culture must become a way of life and activity of every citizen, every official." [5]. Emphasizes the unique role of the Constitution and our laws in the development of legal consciousness and culture of citizens, the fulfillment of duties and responsibilities to the Motherland.

PF of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 - Approved by the Decree No. 5847 "On approval of the Concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", the approved "Concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" identifies the following tasks directly related to the development of ideological and legal competence of students:

- students do not have the skills of critical thinking, independent search, and analysis of information;
- strengthening the spiritual and moral content of higher education, educating young people in the spirit of respect for national values, humanism, and patriotism based on high spiritual ideas, further developing work to strengthen their immunity against foreign ideas and ideologies [6].

DISCUSSION

In today's so-called age of globalization, education and upbringing play an important role in protecting young people from aggressive ideas. After all, education, which has always been carried out in the pursuit of noble goals, has always shown positive results.

Improving the system of spiritual and educational work in our country has always been a priority. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021, No. PP-5040 In the Resolution "On measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational work." "Implement comprehensive measures aimed at eliminating such evils as indifference to the fate of the country, localism, tribalism, corruption, disregard for family values, and irresponsibility in the upbringing of young people; raising the culture of the population's use of the World Wide Web, strengthening legal immunity against ideological and information attacks; culture, literature, cinema, theater, all kinds of music and art, publishing and publishing, spiritual and moral criteria in the media, achieving the priority of national and universal values; regular study of geopolitical and legal processes, terrorism, extremism, bigotry, human trafficking, The effective ideological fight against drug trafficking and other dangerous

threats, as well as the development of international cooperation in this area "[7] were identified as priorities for radical improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work.

Also, from the 2020-2021 academic year the country began to teach "Education" as a subject. This allows for the effective implementation of continuous spiritual education. This opinion is fully confirmed by the following views of the President: Given the importance of relying on the wisdom of the sages, "The better the education, the happier the people." "For education to be perfect, there must be no room for emptiness" [2, p. 505]. As the President noted, the more perfect the education and upbringing of young people, the more they will develop a sense of involvement in the development of society, it also plays an important role in fulfilling its duties and responsibilities to the homeland.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, as an important factor of legal culture in future professionals, the development of ideological and legal competence in future students is closely linked, first of all, with educating them in the spirit of respect for the national idea.

As noted in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on December 28, 2018, "We need to develop a national idea that will be a source of strength for us in carrying out the great tasks set before us." In the process of addressing the Oliy Majlis, these views were not emphasized in vain, of course. Because at a time when ideological threats and legal attacks are intensifying in the world civilization, it is the development of the national idea to protect the youth of our country from various dangers. legal immunity should be formed in young people against evil ideas.

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